

FACTORS AFFECTING THE ROLES AND EMPOWERMENT OF BARANGAY HEALTH WORKERS

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ABSTRACT

The barangay health workers (BHWs) play a vital role in the community since they provide basic healthcare services. It is therefore important to identify the factors that affect how they carry out their roles to think of ways in which they can be empowered, which will also improve the quality of care provided to the community. This study was geared towards determining the extent of factors affecting the roles of the BHWs and to identify the mandated and assumed roles that they perform. It also analyzed if there is a significant difference in the factors affecting the roles of BHWs when grouped according to profile variables. The researchers employed the descriptive-comparative research design. Data was gathered through a survey by floating an adapted questionnaire. There was a total of 146 BHWs who participated in the study. Data was analyzed and interpreted using frequency and percentage counts, weighted means, and ANOVA. The findings show that personal, political, environmental, emotional, and physical factors moderately affect the BHWs. The most frequent mandated role performed is taking anthropometric assessment while providing prenatal care in the absence of healthcare professionals is the most frequently performed assumed role. There was a significant difference in the effects of personal factors when grouped according to educational attainment. The effects of political factors significantly differ in terms of educational attainment and employment status. An IEC material was designed to highlight the key roles of BHWs and the ways in which they can be empowered, with the goal of improving their capacity to serve the community effectively by providing clear, concise information about their mandated roles in healthcare delivery.

Keywords: *assumed roles, emotional factor, environmental factor, mandated roles, personal factor, political factor*

INTRODUCTION

Health is a fundamental human right recognized globally, and access to quality health care is essential to achieving it. Health professionals serve as the backbone of the health system, ensuring the promotion, protection, and restoration of health across all levels of care. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2019) defines Primary Health Care (PHC) as essential health care made universally accessible to individuals and families in the community through their full participation. PHC emphasizes prevention, health education, and community participation to ensure health equity and well-being for all.

In developing countries like the Philippines, access to health services remains uneven due to geographic, economic, and systemic challenges. During community immersion in various barangays of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, the researchers observed issues affecting primary health care delivery. Some health stations were open only once a week, while others had insufficient personnel

or displayed favoritism in service delivery. Many residents lacked awareness of available free health services, and some barangays had too few active health workers to meet community needs. These observations highlight the crucial role and challenges faced by Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) in ensuring accessible, efficient, and equitable health care.

The Philippine government has implemented policies to strengthen community-based health care. Republic Act No. 11223, the Universal Health Care Act of 2019, mandates that all Filipinos have access to comprehensive and quality health services without financial hardship. Earlier, the Aquino Health Agenda and Kalusugang Pangkalahatan emphasized universal coverage and health equity. Central to these efforts are BHWs, who serve as the first link between communities and the formal health system. Under Republic Act No. 7883, the Barangay Health Workers' Benefits and Incentives Act of 1995, a BHW is defined as a trained volunteer who provides primary health care services within the community. The law grants incentives and recognition to BHWs for their vital role in promoting health and preventing disease. They function as health educators, promoters, and basic care providers, particularly in underserved areas. However, despite these legal protections, BHWs often face challenges such as irregular work schedules, inadequate compensation, limited training, and political interference, which hinder consistent service delivery.

According to the Department of Health (DOH, 2023), BHWs perform various functions, including community organizing, health education, disease prevention, and assistance in basic clinical services. They take vital signs, record data, assist in maternal and child care, and help maintain medical supplies. In many communities, they also perform non-mandated tasks such as distributing medications, assisting in immunizations, and conducting home visits. These roles make them indispensable in achieving public health goals, yet their effectiveness depends on multiple factors influencing their work environment and motivation. Numerous studies have explored BHWs' challenges and contributions. Abelardo et al. (2021) and Hartigan-Go et al. (2023) identified workload, limited resources, and lack of support as major barriers. Taburnal (2017, 2020) highlighted personal, political, and environmental factors influencing BHW performance. Despite these findings, limited research examines how these factors collectively affect their empowerment and role fulfillment, especially at the local level.

This study is anchored on Role Theory (Merton, 1957), which posits that individuals' behaviors are shaped by expectations linked to their roles. BHWs' effectiveness depends on how well they internalize and perform their roles amid community and institutional expectations. Complementing this is Erikson's Psychosocial Theory, which emphasizes that fulfilling meaningful roles contributes to an individual's sense of purpose and identity. These frameworks help explain how BHWs' sense of role clarity and empowerment influences their performance. This study assumes that the profile of BHWs—including age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, length of service, and training—affects how personal, political, environmental, emotional, and physical factors influence their roles. The research differentiates between mandated roles (as defined by DOH) and assumed roles (voluntary duties performed beyond their official scope). Understanding these relationships can help develop targeted interventions to empower BHWs and improve community health service delivery.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to describe the roles of the barangay health workers of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya and determined the different factors affecting these roles. As the main output, an IEC material was developed to empower BHWs. The research was conducted during the school year 2024-2025. Specifically, it sought answers to the following problems:

1. What is the profile of the BHWs in terms of:
 - a. Age;
 - b. Sex;
 - c. Civil Status;
 - d. Educational Attainment;
 - e. Employment Status;
 - f. Length of Service as a BHW; and
 - g. The number of Health Care Trainings Attended?
2. What is the level of effect of the following factors on the roles of barangay health workers?
 - a. Personal
 - b. Political
 - c. Environmental
 - d. Emotional
 - e. Physical
3. What are the assumed roles of the barangay health workers as their responsibility aside from what is stated in the law?
4. Is there a significant difference between the level of effects of the factors on the roles of BHWs when grouped according to their profile variables?
5. What IEC Material can be produced to empower BHWs in their health roles?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive-comparative research design to describe the demographic profiles, mandated and assumed roles, and factors affecting the performance of Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. It also compared the levels of these factors when grouped according to selected profile variables. The study was conducted in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, the provincial capital and a first-class municipality located in the Cagayan Valley Region. There were 146 respondents who are BHWs assigned to the 25 barangays of Bayombong, as listed by the Bayombong Municipal Health Office (2023). Because the total population of BHWs was relatively small and unevenly distributed across barangays, total enumeration sampling was employed.

BHWs below 60 years old and actively serving during the data collection period were included in the study. Excluded from participation were those aged 60 years and above, as well as health professionals or graduates of health-related programs working in the barangays. Respondents' eligibility was confirmed through the informed consent process, which involved verifying age, educational background, and employment status.

Data were collected using a researcher-modified survey questionnaire adapted from the works of Taburnal (2017), “*Barangay Health Workers’ Level of Competence*,” and Taburnal (2020), “*Knowledge and Competence of Barangay Health Workers*.” The modified tool underwent pilot testing among 20 BHWs in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya.

Surveys were conducted face-to-face at times convenient for the participants, often during periods when barangay health stations were least busy. All completed questionnaires were securely stored and later encoded into a single file for statistical analysis. Frequency count, percent, mean, and standard deviation were used to describe the respondents in terms of their socio-demographic profile variables, and mean and standard deviation to determine the level of the effect of predominant factors on the roles of the BHWs in the delivery of basic health services. An independent sample t-test was used to compare the levels of effect of the different factors in terms of sex. In terms of the other profile variables, one-way ANOVA was utilized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1. Profile of the Barangay Health Workers (BHWs)

When categorized by age, most of the respondents fall within the 40 to 49 years age group (33.9%), while the least represented group is those aged 18 to 29 years (12.5%). The data indicates that nearly all respondents are female, accounting for 99.1%, with only one male respondent, which represents 0.9%. Regarding civil status, majority of respondents are married (82.1%), and only one respondent is a widower (0.9%). In terms of educational attainment, most respondents have completed high school (47.3%), while the fewest have completed only elementary education (8.9%). The survey findings reveal that a significant portion of respondents are unemployed (42%), with the least number being self-employed (18.8%). When considering the length of service as barangay health workers (BHW), majority of respondents have served for less than a year to five years (67%). Conversely, only 2.7% of respondents have been in service for 21 to 25 years. Furthermore, a significant majority of respondents (91.1%) have attended 1 to 8 health care training programs.

Section 2. Factors That Affect the Roles of BHWs

Table 3

Personal Factors

Statements	Mean	SD	QD
1 Formal education related to current work	2.33	1.42	Slightly Affects
2 Need for trainings and seminars	3.29	1.49	Moderately Affects
3 Self-confidence in healthcare services delivery	3.21	1.47	Moderately Affects
4 Personal beliefs/attitudes/ interests/ practices towards work are different from the client	3.00	1.47	Moderately Affects
5 Communication skills, verbal, and nonverbal	2.97	1.37	Moderately Affects
6 Management and leadership style	2.99	1.50	Moderately Affects
7 Use of technology to facilitate healthcare delivery	3.13	1.40	Moderately Affects
Overall	2.99	1.14	Moderately Affects

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Does not affect (DNA); 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly affects (SA); 2.50 – 3.49: Moderately affects (MA); 3.50 – 4.49: Affects (A); 4.50 – 5.00: Greatly affects (GA)

The results reveal that personal factors moderately affect the roles and performance of Barangay Health Workers (BHWs), with an overall computed mean of 2.99 (SD = 1.14). Notably, the need for training and seminars emerged as the highest-rated item with a mean of 3.29, qualitatively described as moderately affects. The result implies that BHWs perceive continuous education and professional development as essential components in fulfilling their responsibilities effectively. Since BHWs serve as the community's first line of contact for health concerns and emergencies, they must be equipped with adequate knowledge and skills to provide competent and immediate care.

In contrast, formal education related to current work obtained the lowest computed mean of 2.33 (SD = 1.42), interpreted as slightly affects. This finding suggests that formal academic attainment does not have a substantial influence on the effectiveness of BHWs in performing their duties. Instead, practical experience, hands-on exposure, and continuous learning opportunities are more influential in improving their competency. As supported by Carrillo et al. (2023) and Taburnal (2020), ongoing training and seminars significantly enhance the quality of patient care and ensure safety in community health practice. Therefore, strengthening training initiatives and institutional support systems is vital to improving BHW performance and community health outcomes.

Table 4

Political Factors

Statements	Mean	SD	QD
1 Harmonious relationship with barangay officials	3.01	1.37	Moderately Affects
2 Support of barangay officials to health programs and activities	2.99	1.37	Moderately Affects
3 Concern of barangay officials to the condition of barangay health center and support facility	3.06	1.32	Moderately Affects
4 Fund allocation of the barangay officials to trainings and seminars of BHW	3.13	1.42	Moderately Affects
5 Honorarium is received/paid on time	2.68	1.45	Moderately Affects
6 Duties and responsibilities are well defined	3.00	1.54	Moderately Affects
7 Replacement of BHW when barangay officials change	3.22	1.39	Moderately Affects
8 Relationship with municipal local government unit officials	3.03	1.51	Moderately Affects
Overall	3.02	1.13	Moderately Affects

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Does not affect (DNA); 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly affects (SA); 2.50 – 3.49: Moderately affects (MA); 3.50 – 4.49: Affects (A); 4.50 – 5.00: Greatly affects (GA)

Findings indicate that political factors moderately affect the performance of Barangay Health Workers (BHWs), with an overall computed mean of 3.02 (SD = 1.13). All items under this category were perceived to have a moderate influence, suggesting that political dynamics within the barangay environment play a significant yet not overwhelming role in shaping BHW engagement and stability. Among the political indicators, the replacement of BHWs when barangay officials change obtained the highest computed mean of 3.22 (SD = 1.39), indicating it as the most influential factor. Respondents revealed that there are no standardized guidelines governing the retention or replacement of BHWs, making their tenure largely dependent on the discretion of local leaders. This practice creates insecurity and instability, as political transitions often result in the replacement of experienced BHWs regardless of performance or tenure. Thus, BHW appointments and continuance in service must be based on merit, competence, and community service record rather than political affiliation. Institutionalizing fair and transparent selection criteria can ensure continuity and professionalism in community healthcare delivery.

Conversely, the timely receipt of honorarium recorded the lowest computed mean of 2.68 (SD = 1.45), suggesting it is the least influential political factor. Despite financial challenges and delayed incentives, BHWs remain motivated by their commitment to serve, particularly the marginalized sectors of the community. Nonetheless, increasing their honorarium and providing additional benefits can serve as positive reinforcement, enhancing their performance and morale. Consistent with Ramirez et al. (2019), effective local governance—through adequate funding, legislative support, and recognition of BHW contributions—plays a crucial role in sustaining health programs and ensuring community well-being.

Table 5*Environmental Factors*

Statements	Mean	SD	QD
1 Timely transport of supplies to health care facilities	2.95	1.35	Moderately Affects
2 Proper information and communication system	2.91	1.36	Moderately Affects
3 Appropriate care/utilization of records and reports	2.96	1.42	Moderately Affects
4 Enough supplies, materials, and equipment	3.04	1.15	Moderately Affects
5 Condition of barangay health station and support facility	2.97	1.24	Moderately Affects
6 Active participation of the community in the prevention of illnesses and promotion of wellness	2.96	1.38	Moderately Affects
Overall	2.97	1.11	Moderately Affects

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Does not affect (DNA); 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly affects (SA); 2.50 – 3.49: Moderately affects (MA); 3.50 – 4.49: Affects (A); 4.50 – 5.00: Greatly affects (GA)

Environmental factors were found to moderately affect Barangay Health Workers (BHWs), with an overall computed mean of 2.97 (SD = 1.11). The availability of supplies, materials, and equipment obtained the highest mean of 3.04 (SD = 1.15), indicating it as the most influential factor. Insufficient medical supplies, limited facilities, and outdated equipment—such as only one BP set or weighing scale per barangay—hinder efficient healthcare delivery and contribute to residents seeking services elsewhere. Conversely, effective information and communication systems had the lowest mean of 2.91 (SD = 1.36), suggesting minimal influence, though digital barriers like poor internet access, lack of gadgets, and low digital literacy still affect coordination. While communication platforms like Messenger aid in information sharing, basic digital literacy training is needed. Consistent with Carrillo et al. (2023) and Taburnal (2020), environmental resources and infrastructure directly influence BHW competence and the overall quality of community health services.

Table 6*Emotional Factors*

Statements	Mean	SD	QD
1 Love for work (perform work religiously)	3.14	1.75	Moderately Affects
2 Feel that you are part of the health system through supportive supervision and appropriate training	3.18	1.65	Moderately Affects
3 Willingness to conduct voluntary service	3.04	1.65	Moderately Affects
4 Self-fulfillment when providing service to people	3.15	1.73	Moderately Affects

5	Willing to exert extra effort for the sake of the organization	3.08	1.67	Moderately Affects
Overall		3.12	1.57	Moderately Affects

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Does not affect (DNA); 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly affects (SA); 2.50 – 3.49: Moderately affects (MA); 3.50 – 4.49: Affects (A); 4.50 – 5.00: Greatly affects (GA)

Emotional factors were found to moderately affect Barangay Health Workers (BHWs), with an overall computed mean of 3.12 (SD = 1.57). The item with the highest mean, feeling part of the healthcare system through supportive supervision and training (3.18, SD = 1.65), indicates that emotional connection and recognition have the greatest impact on BHW motivation. Respondents reported feeling undervalued due to limited financial and moral support from barangay officials, with some even covering training expenses themselves. Conversely, the willingness to conduct voluntary service had the lowest mean (3.04, SD = 1.65), showing that while BHWs face challenges, their commitment and resilience remain strong. However, sustained motivation requires emotional validation, inclusion in decision-making, and access to professional development. These findings highlight the need for local governments to strengthen emotional and psychosocial support mechanisms to enhance the morale, volunteerism, and overall performance of BHWs in community health service delivery.

Table 7

Physical Factors

	Statements	Mean	SD	QD
1	Having adequate food and supply and proper nutrition	2.94	1.48	Moderately Affects
2	Long working hours	2.93	1.34	Moderately Affects
3	Too many paper-works to finish	3.06	1.23	Moderately Affects
4	Exhaustion in work	2.79	1.38	Moderately Affects
Overall		2.93	1.11	Moderately Affects

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Does not affect (DNA); 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly affects (SA); 2.50 – 3.49: Moderately affects (MA); 3.50 – 4.49: Affects (A); 4.50 – 5.00: Greatly affects (GA)

The findings reveal that physical factors moderately affect Barangay Health Workers (BHWs), with an overall computed mean of 2.93 (SD = 1.11). The most significant factor is “too much paperwork to finish” (mean = 3.06), highlighting that administrative tasks consume much of the BHWs’ time, limiting their ability to focus on community health services. Many BHWs serve large populations, including numerous pregnant women and children, and are also tasked with census duties required by the Philippine Statistics Authority. These responsibilities often lead to fatigue and time constraints. Conversely, “exhaustion from work” has the lowest mean (2.79), indicating that despite their heavy workload, most BHWs remain committed and find fulfillment in serving their communities. However, the study underscores the need for better task delegation, organized scheduling, and administrative support to reduce physical strain and prevent burnout while maintaining efficient health service delivery at the barangay level.

Section 3. Roles of BHWs

The findings reveal that all Barangay Health Workers (100%) perform anthropometric assessments, making it the most commonly executed task since it serves as the initial and baseline assessment for patients seeking care in barangay health centers. In contrast, only 15.2% of BHWs are

involved in collecting sputum, urine, and stool samples, as these procedures are primarily conducted in higher-level health facilities such as rural health units and hospitals. Additionally, 35.7% of BHWs provide prenatal care in the absence of healthcare professionals, especially in remote areas where they coordinate closely with midwives and community health nurses. The least performed role is administering medications without guidance (8.9%), as BHWs recognize the risks of unsupervised medication administration. Despite this, they play a crucial role in educating residents about the safe use of prescribed medicines, avoiding self-medication, and promoting proper health-seeking behaviors in their communities.

Section 4. Significant Differences in the Factors Affecting the BHWs When Grouped According to Profile Variables

Table 9

Personal Factors with Demographic Profiles of BHWs

Profile	Groups	f	Mean	SD	QD	F-value	p-value
Age	18-29	14	3.16	1.24	MA	1.247 ^{ns}	0.296
	30-39	27	2.68	1.06	MA		
	40-49	38	3.20	1.23	MA		
	50-59	33	2.93	1.03	MA		
Civil Status	Single	16	3.04	1.20	MA	1.530 ^{ns}	0.211
	Married	92	2.97	1.12	MA		
Educational Attainment	Elementary	10	3.69 ^A	0.75	A	3.025*	0.043
	High School	53	2.78 ^B	1.18	MA		
	College	49	3.08 ^B	1.11	MA		
Employment Status	Employed	44	2.83	1.15	MA	0.866 ^{ns}	0.424
	Unemployed	47	3.04	1.20	MA		
	Self-employed	21	3.22	0.98	MA		
Length of Service as a BHW	0 to 5	75	2.97	1.18	MA	0.896 ^{ns}	0.469
	6 to 10	18	3.28	1.19	MA		
	11 to 15	12	3.07	0.80	MA		
Number of Health Care Training Attended	1 to 8	102	3.02	1.16	MA	0.675 ^{ns}	0.569
	9 to 18	7	2.80	0.90	MA		

*Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Does not affect (DNA); 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly affects (SA); 2.50 – 3.49: Moderately affects (MA); 3.50 – 4.49: Affects (A); 4.50 – 5.00: Greatly affects (GA); ns- not significant; *significant at $\alpha=0.05$*

The study revealed no significant difference in the personal factors affecting Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) when grouped according to age, civil status, employment status, length of service, and number of health-related trainings attended. However, a significant difference ($F = 3.025$; $p = 0.043$) was observed based on educational attainment, with BHWs who completed only elementary education being more affected by personal factors than those with higher education levels. This finding indicates that educational background influences how BHWs perceive and manage the personal factors impacting their roles. Supporting this, Vera-Toscano et al. (2017) emphasized that continuous education and adult learning significantly enhance volunteer performance, as skills

evolve through experience and informal training. Therefore, even after formal schooling, opportunities for lifelong learning and professional development remain essential in improving the competencies and adaptability of BHWs in effectively fulfilling their community health responsibilities.

Table 10
Political Factors with Demographic Profiles of BHWs

Profile	Groups	f	Mean	SD	QD	F-value	p-value
Age	18-29	14	2.82	0.91	MA	1.508 ^{ns}	0.217
	30-39	27	2.68	1.07	MA		
	40-49	38	3.21	1.16	MA		
	50-59	33	3.15	1.19	MA		
Civil Status	Single	16	2.98	0.99	MA	0.552 ^{ns}	0.648
	Married	92	3.02	1.16	MA		
Educational Attainment	Elementary	10	3.73 ^A	0.53	A	5.863 ^{**}	0.004
	High School	53	2.67 ^C	1.10	MA		
	College	49	3.24 ^B	1.15	MA		
Employment Status	Employed	44	2.69 ^B	0.94	MA	3.303 [*]	0.040
	Unemployed	47	3.16 ^A	1.24	MA		
	Self-employed	21	3.36 ^A	1.12	MA		
Length of Service as a BHW	0 to 5	75	2.97	1.13	MA	1.085 ^{ns}	0.368
	6 to 10	18	3.35	1.21	MA		
	11 to 15	12	3.14	1.02	MA		
Number of Health Care Training Attended	0 to 8	102	3.05	1.14	MA	0.329 ^{ns}	0.804
	9 to 18	7	2.82	1.29	MA		

*Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Does not affect (DNA); 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly affects (SA); 2.50 – 3.49: Moderately affects (MA); 3.50 – 4.49: Affects (A); 4.50 – 5.00: Greatly affects (GA); ns- not significant; *significant at $\alpha=0.05$; **significant at $\alpha=0.01$*

The study found significant differences in the effects of political factors on Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) when grouped by educational attainment ($F = 5.863$; $p = 0.004$) and employment status ($F = 3.303$; $p = 0.040$). Respondents with only elementary education and those who were self-employed perceived stronger political influences than their counterparts. This may be attributed to job insecurity caused by political turnover, where newly elected officials often replace existing BHWs. Retention should therefore be based on performance, willingness to learn, and community feedback rather than political affiliation. Self-employed BHWs also face added vulnerability due to unstable income and limited LGU support. Supporting studies by Dhar (2011), the NCSA (2022), Shaffril et al. (2010), and Choi (2012) emphasize that education, diversity, and merit-based systems improve workplace stability. Hence, promoting transparency and inclusivity can reduce political interference and enhance BHW effectiveness.

Table 11*Environmental Factors with Demographic Profiles of BHWs*

Profile	Groups	f	Mean	SD	QD	F-value	p-value
Age	18-29	14	2.98	1.00	MA	0.749 ^{ns}	0.525
	30-39	27	2.69	1.06	MA		
	40-49	38	3.05	1.16	MA		
	50-59	33	3.09	1.14	MA		
Civil Status	Single	16	2.93	1.13	MA	0.13 ^{ns}	0.942
	Married	92	2.97	1.13	MA		
Educational Attainment	Elementary	10	3.23	0.49	MA	2.468 ^{ns}	0.09
	High School	53	2.72	1.06	MA		
	College	49	3.17	1.22	MA		
Employment Status	Employed	44	2.73	1.06	MA	1.688 ^{ns}	0.19
	Unemployed	47	3.12	1.10	MA		
	Self-employed	21	3.13	1.22	MA		
Length of Service as a BHW	0 to 5	75	2.94	1.13	MA	0.224 ^{ns}	0.924
	6 to 10	18	3.02	1.18	MA		
	11 to 15	12	3.18	1.06	MA		
Number of Health Care Attended	1 to 8	102	2.97	1.13	MA	0.383 ^{ns}	0.765
	9 to 18	7	3.12	1.04	MA		

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Does not affect (DNA); 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly affects (SA); 2.50 – 3.49: Moderately affects (MA); 3.50 – 4.49: Affects (A); 4.50 – 5.00: Greatly affects (GA); ns- not significant

The study found no significant difference in how environmental factors affect Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) when grouped according to age, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, length of service, and training attended. This indicates that BHWs share a common experience of environmental challenges regardless of demographic differences. Abelardo et al. (2021) support this finding, revealing that BHWs in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas face similar obstacles such as poor transportation, inadequate medical supplies, and substandard barangay health facilities. These systemic issues hinder the consistent delivery of healthcare services across all settings. The results emphasize that environmental barriers are universal among BHWs and not dependent on personal factors. Thus, there is a pressing need for government and local health authorities to invest in infrastructure, logistics, and resource allocation. Strengthening environmental support systems would empower BHWs to perform their duties effectively and ensure equitable health service delivery in all communities.

Table 12*Emotional Factors with Demographic Profiles of BHWs*

Profile	Groups	f	Mean	SD	QD	F-value	p-value
Age	18-29	14	3.51	1.75	A	2.245 ^{ns}	0.087
	30-39	27	2.68	1.47	MA		
	40-49	38	3.52	1.52	A		
	50-59	33	2.84	1.53	MA		

Civil Status	Single	16	2.86	1.47	MA	1.595 ^{ns}	0.195
	Married	92	3.14	1.58	MA		
Educational Attainment	Elementary	10	4.04	1.28	A	2.901 ^{ns}	0.059
	High School	53	2.83	1.52	MA		
	College	49	3.24	1.61	MA		
Employment Status	Employed	44	3.07	1.55	MA	0.036 ^{ns}	0.965
	Unemployed	47	3.15	1.64	MA		
	Self-employed	21	3.15	1.53	MA		
Length of Service as a BHW	0 to 5	75	3.13	1.58	MA	0.603 ^{ns}	0.661
	6 to 10	18	3.11	1.69	MA		
	11 to 15	12	3.48	1.50	MA		
Number of Health Care Training Attended	0 to 8	102	3.16	1.58	MA	0.843 ^{ns}	0.473
	9 to 18	7	2.97	1.58	MA		

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Does not affect (DNA); 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly affects (SA); 2.50 – 3.49: Moderately affects (MA); 3.50 – 4.49: Affects (A); 4.50 – 5.00: Greatly affects (GA); ns- not significant

The study found no significant difference in how emotional factors affect Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) when grouped according to profile variables, indicating that emotional influences are experienced similarly across all demographics. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (2001) explains that emotional well-being is shaped by external factors—such as leadership, organizational support, and workplace culture—through cognitive and emotional processes. When BHWs feel supported and psychologically safe (Kahn, 1990), they become more confident and committed in fulfilling their roles. Furthermore, their sense of fulfillment and purpose reflects an alignment between personal and professional values, consistent with Schwartz's (2000) and Bardi and Schwartz's (2003) findings that behaviors aligned with one's values foster motivation and goal achievement. This uniformity in emotional perception highlights that motivation among BHWs stems more from shared values and intrinsic purpose rather than demographic differences. Hence, fostering supportive and value-driven environments is vital to sustaining their emotional resilience and performance.

Table 13

Physical Factors with Demographic Profiles of BHWs

Profile	Groups	f	Mean	SD	QD	F-value	p-value
Age	18-29	14	3.21	1.28	MA	0.989 ^{ns}	0.401
	30-39	27	2.74	1.12	MA		
	40-49	38	3.09	1.13	MA		
	50-59	33	2.79	1.01	MA		
Civil Status	Single	16	2.55	1.02	MA	1.752 ^{ns}	0.161
	Married	92	2.97	1.12	MA		
Educational Attainment	Elementary	10	3.40	0.97	MA	1.219 ^{ns}	0.300
	High School	53	2.81	1.03	MA		
	College	49	2.96	1.22	MA		

Employment Status	Employed	44	2.98	1.30	MA	0.323 ^{ns}	0.725
	Unemployed	47	2.84	0.98	MA		
	Self-employed	21	3.05	1.02	MA		
Length of Service as a BHW	0 to 5	75	2.90	1.19	MA	0.568 ^{ns}	0.687
	6 to 10	18	2.88	0.92	MA		
	11 to 15	12	3.33	1.07	MA		
Number of Health Care Training Attended	0 to 8	102	2.93	1.13	MA	0.011 ^{ns}	0.998
	9 to 18	7	2.93	1.20	MA		

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Does not affect (DNA); 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly affects (SA); 2.50 – 3.49: Moderately affects (MA); 3.50 – 4.49: Affects (A); 4.50 – 5.00: Greatly affects (GA); ns- not significant

The study revealed that there is no significant difference in how physical factors affect Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) when grouped according to age, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, length of service, or number of healthcare trainings attended. This indicates that physical challenges, such as workload, mobility, and environmental conditions, are commonly experienced by all BHWs, regardless of demographic differences. Similar findings were reported by Carbonell et al. (2012), who found that BHWs in Dasmariñas City faced comparable stressors, including work overload, limited communication with supervisors, and difficulty balancing work and personal life. Despite these challenges, BHWs generally maintained control over their tasks, felt recognized for their efforts, and did not report significant physical or emotional strain. Overall, these findings highlight the shared resilience and adaptability of BHWs and emphasize the importance of implementing systemic improvements—such as fair workload distribution, supportive supervision, and better physical resources—to enhance their working conditions and well-being.

Section 5. Information Education and Communication Material

An information education and communication (IEC) material was developed by the researchers based on the findings of the study. Since the study found out that there are frequently, rarely, and even totally not performed roles, the IEC material imparts tips on how the BHWs' roles can be performed accurately and effectively. The material also provides a short overview of the roles of BHWs and their importance in the community.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The study reveals that the majority of respondents are aged between 40 and 49 years. Most have completed high school and are self-employed. The majority of them are married and have served as barangay health workers (BHWs) for less than a year to up to five years. Almost all participants are female, with only one male BHW.

All identified factors moderately affect the roles of BHWs. The most significant personal factor is the need for training. Politically, the replacement of BHWs when barangay officials change occurs to the highest extent. In terms of environmental factors, the adequacy of supplies, materials, and equipment significantly impacts BHWs. Emotionally, feeling integrated into the healthcare system

through supportive supervision and appropriate training affects the performance of BHWs. Lastly, the main physical factor impacting BHWs is the burden of excessive paperwork.

Taking anthropometric assessments is a mandated responsibility that is consistently performed by all barangay health workers (BHWs), while providing prenatal care in the absence of healthcare professionals is an assumed role that BHWs frequently undertake to fill gaps in service delivery. Respondents significantly differ in their experiences of personal factors, with BHWs who have only completed elementary education being more affected by these factors. Additionally, those with an elementary education as well as those who are self-employed are more negatively impacted by political factors. However, BHWs do not significantly differ in how they experience environmental, emotional, and physical factors when grouped according to their profile variables.

Recommendations

The following recommendations surfaced from the findings of the study which are directed toward governing bodies with the authority to implement policies and programs:

1. Provide ongoing training, seminars, and capacity-building programs every year
2. Create steady linkages with the government and non-governmental organizations to sustain the availability and timely provision of medical supplies, materials, and equipment to support BHWs' tasks
3. Strengthen barangay leadership support through mentorship, peer support programs, recognition, and incentives to foster a sense of belonging in the health care system
4. Implement simplified documentation or provide digital tools and clerical assistance
5. Provide specialized training in key areas like prenatal care to ensure competency when assisting in the absence of healthcare professionals.
6. Offer refresher courses for BHWs with limited formal education to bridge knowledge gaps.
7. Establish standardized criteria for hiring and retaining BHWs based on qualifications and experience rather than political affiliations.
8. To the barangay health workers to engage in training and skills workshops at least two times a year, participate in IT training for digital record keeping, and collaborate with local leaders and health professionals for support.
9. To future researchers to conduct similar research with a qualitative research method and in other municipalities or regions to compare findings and identify broader trends.
10. To include the senior citizens (≥ 60 years old) as respondents in future similar studies and include a larger and more diverse sample of BHWs, particularly increasing the representation of male BHWs for a more balanced perspective.
11. Study the long-term effects of training programs on BHW performance and healthcare outcomes in the community, a post-intervention assessment.

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